

EXTRA LINGUISTIC ISSUES IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION
WORLDVIEW, RITUALS, CUSTOMS

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Abstract: Worldview in intercultural communication represents an intercultural adaptation of worldview research originally from the humanities, theology, philosophy, and social sciences, particularly anthropology and linguistics. The concept refers to cognitive structures and holistic belief systems often shared by members of a culture perceived to influence one's life space intersecting with deeply held assumptions on topics such as events, relationships, natural forces, deity, power, social hierarchy, and change that explain not only one's cognitive map but also communication regarding current experiences and future event predictions.

Key words: *linguistic issues, communication, rituals, customs, researchers.*

The notion can be said to inform the deepest layers of a culture's experience. Some scholars trace the modern use of the concept to the 19th century with Humboldt's application of the terms *Weltanschauung* and *Weltbegriff*, referring to beliefs defining how a culture or an individual interprets and interacts with the world. In sum, intercultural worldview is a quasi-metaphysical mental map influencing one's thinking, doing, communicating, and discernment of others, nature, and self.¹ Worldview in intercultural communication has early roots in linguistics, such as from Wilhelm von Humboldt's 19th-century underpinnings, as thoroughly reviewed in Underhill 2012. Lucy 1997 articulates additional developments in early language and culture research and theory, captured in the well-known Sapir-Whorf hypothesis. Anthropologists noting worldview were highly influenced in the early 20th century by Ruth Benedict's holistic culture and functionality, as Redfield 1953, Hall 1976, and Kearney 1984 describe. Philosophical interests persist in understanding orientations and practices, as Note, et al. 2009 states. In texts focused on intercultural communication, intercultural worldview was specifically addressed in Sarbaugh 1979, with an early emphasis on identifying control over nature, as multiple cognitive orientations, and as religious outlooks such as those in Kraft 1978 reveal. Gudykunst and Kim 1997 emphasizes the need to underlying factors, in new developments of assessing worldview in intercultural communication.

¹ Abramson, N. R., Lane, H. W. Nagai, H., & Takagi, H. (1993). A comparison of Canadian and Japanese cognitive styles: Implications for management interaction. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 24(3), 575-588.

Overall, intercultural communication researchers appear to consider worldview as a deeply structured, fundamental cultural model functioning to interpret communication and understanding among cultures. We believe that special attention should be paid to culture-specific factors when characterizing the efficacy of communication, because numerous investigations indicate that they are key and positive factors that enhance the negotiation and decision-making processes, stimulate the performance of multicultural teams members, and increase their satisfaction and decrease work absence. The relation between culture/cultural diversity and the efficacy of their communication in a multicultural environment needs to be continuously explored due to globalization processes and internationalization of European companies, especially in the context of the recent frequent political attempts to get Chinese and European business collaboration closer than ever before.²

This is why it is worth diverting researchers attention from intercultural communication practices between East Asians, Americans and Western Europeans onto Central Europeans, as new international businesses will possibly place many of Central European employees in new cultural contexts.

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